

Virtual Try-on using Augmented Reality

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Abstract—In the beauty industry, augmented reality (AR)-based virtual try-on technology is rising in popularity. Customers can use this technology to virtually apply cosmetics on their faces to see how various products will look on them. Users can virtually try makeup without wasting any materials or time. An RGBD camera is used to recognize and track facial features. This seminar paper presents an analysis of virtual try-on makeup products using AR technology and integration of machine learning algorithms to enhance the virtual try-on experience.

Keywords—Virtual Makeup, Augmented Reality, Facial Landmarks, Dlib, OpenCV

I. INTRODUCTION

The beauty industry is one of the fastest-growing and constantly evolving industries worldwide. With the rise of e-commerce, customers are increasingly purchasing beauty products online, making it challenging to determine which products will work best for them. And also the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the beauty industry, with many brick-and-mortar stores closing and customers turning to online shopping. However purchasing beauty products online can be challenging for customers, as they are unable to physically try on products before making a purchase. This is where virtual try-on technology using augmented reality (AR) has emerged as a promising solution, allowing customers to try on makeup products virtually from the safety of their homes. AR technology overlays digital images of makeup products onto a live video feed of the customer's face, creating a seamless and interactive virtual try-on experience. In this paper, we will delve into the technical aspects of virtual try-on makeup products using AR technology and discuss the benefits of this technology for the beauty industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Zheng Chong and Lingfei Mo in [1] explore the ST-VTON, a two-stage self-supervised try-on method that can produce photo-realistic try-on outcomes using simple human photos and a typical ViT structure. The authors point out that earlier virtual try-on techniques frequently called for paired data, which is expensive and challenging to get. The self-supervised learning framework on which ST-VTON is based allows it to learn from unpaired data. The authors test ST-VTON on two sizable datasets and demonstrate that it performs better than cutting-edge techniques in terms of visual quality and variety. They claim that ST-VTON has the potential to be helpful in applications including online

shopping, customized fashion design, and virtual try-ons for clothing.

Aline de Fatima Soares Borges in [2] has presented an augmented reality system that allows the user to apply virtual makeup directly on the user's face using one finger or any similar shape object. The user can select the product and other features while interacting with it thanks to its interface. Additionally, a real-time prototype was implemented using a standard PC and an Intel RealSense RGBD camera to take colour and depth images. The user's face is tracked, along with 91 facial landmarks, and mapped to a normalized facial space that is unaffected by facial expressions and movements. The virtual makeup that has been applied to the face is stored in this normalized space. A mesh with 124 triangles represents the normalized face. The study also offers a precise real-time face touch detection method that monitors the face and the tip of the finger in depth and recognizes touch events when the finger's distance from the face changes.

Tariq Masooda, Johannes Egger in [3] explore adopting augmented reality in the age of industrial digitalization. Based on field tests, this report outlines key success factors and problems for industrial augmented reality (IAR) installation initiatives. Through 22 experiments carried out in business and academia, this study sought to address the research question, "What are the challenges and success factors for the implementation of industrial augmented reality?" The purpose of this study was to address the research question, "What are the challenges and success factors for the implementation of industrial augmented reality?" using 22 experiments that were carried out in both industry and academia. The industry should take into account the organizational components of the implementation, even if this research has shown that the technological environment is the key to a successful IAR deployment.

Yu-I Yang, Chih-Kai Yang, Chih-Hsing Chu in [4] demonstrate a system for depth-sensing technologies used in commercial footwear design review. The device enables customers to visually try on 3D shoe models in a live video stream in a mixed-reality setting. For the purpose of accurately aligning shoe models to moving feet during the try-on procedure, a two-stage object tracking method was created. An iterative closest point (ICP) algorithm that superimposed the recorded depth data and predetermined reference foot models was used to drive the tracking. Future research can build on this work by addressing the functional evaluation of shoe design (such as estimating and improving wear comfort) and

simulating shoe model deformation under various foot motions. The tracking procedure in the current system only employs one reference foot model, which might not work effectively for all users.

Jung-Hwan Kim a, Minjeong Kim b , Minjung Park c in [5]. This study compared the effects of AR and VR on vividness/interactivity, a sense of presence, users' sensory brand app experience, attitude, and behavioural intention based on the concepts of the Reality-Virtuality (RV) continuum and the stimulus-organism-response (S-O-R) framework. The use of AR and VR in retail will increase in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and widespread customer shift to online shopping. But this study has some limitations. That is in this study, the AR/VR experiments were not combined with a sense of touch. When AR/VR shopping are paired with haptic devices, consumers can realistically feel objects in their own hands and have more immersive engaging experiences. And also this study concentrated on general consumer views in connection to consumers' impressions of AR and VR. Studies have addressed detrimental elements like data sharing and dizziness.

Ali Pourramezan Fard, Mohammad H. Mahoor in [6] proposes a unique architecture for the facial landmark recognition challenge that was motivated by the KD (knowledge distillation) notion. Numerous facial image analysis applications require the crucial step of facial landmark detection. In this paper they defined the words "mean-landmark," "soft landmark," and "hard landmark" and used them to train their suggested "tough teacher" and "tolerant teacher" networks. The proposed architecture can potentially be used in other similar computer vision tasks such as body-joint tracking.

Francesca Bonettia , Gary Warnabyb , and Lee Quinna in [7] gives a thorough analysis and synthesis of the research that has been done so far on the application of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in offline and online retailing. The authors talk about how AR and VR might improve the shopping experience, boost sales, and give customers tailored advice in the retail industry. Along with technical obstacles, financial constraints, and user acceptance, they also look at the drawbacks and restrictions of AR and VR. In addition to suggesting a study agenda for future investigations, the paper identifies various research gaps in the body of existing knowledge. The usefulness of AR and VR in boosting consumer engagement and satisfaction, the impact of AR and VR on shop design and layout, and the ethical and privacy issues of deploying AR and VR in retail contexts are some of the topics the authors advise researching.

Bochao Wang, Huabin Zheng , Xiaodan Liang, Yimin Chen, Liang Lin, and Meng Yang in [8] proposes a virtual try-on network that can generate high-quality images of a person wearing clothes that they are not physically wearing. The authors note that previous methods have struggled to generate images that preserve the characteristics of the person, such as their body shape and pose. To address this, they propose a new framework that includes a characteristic-preserving network and an image-based rendering network. The characteristic-preserving network is responsible for preserving the characteristics of the person, while the

rendering network generates the final image. Overall, the paper suggests a feasible technique for virtual try-on that addresses a few drawbacks of earlier approaches. However, additional study is required to assess the method's generalizability and address other difficulties in virtual try-on, such as managing complicated clothing materials and producing realistic images from various angles.

Xintong Han, Zuxuan Wu, Zhe Wu, Ruichi Yu, Larry S. Davis in [9] presents a novel approach for virtual try-on using deep neural networks. The suggested network, known as VITON, takes a reference image of a person and a target article of clothing as inputs and produces a new image that mixes the two, making it appear as though the person is wearing the target item. A spatial transformer network (STN) that aligns the reference image with the target object and a try-on network that creates the final output image make up the two primary parts of the network. The VITON network is a promising method for virtual try-on, but there are still certain issues that need to be resolved, such as the challenge of managing intricate clothing textures and poses. The authors propose that future studies could concentrate on enhancing the alignment procedure and investigating novel loss functions to further enhance the performance of the network.

Aditya Nugroho, Wei-Tsong Wang in [10] investigates the consumer switching behavior to an augmented reality beauty product application using a push-pull mooring theory framework. The impacts of perceived usefulness, perceived attractiveness, social influence, and switching costs on consumers' intentions to switch to the AR beauty product application were investigated in an empirical study by the authors with 254 participants. The study's findings revealed that perceived usefulness and attractiveness significantly increased consumers' intentions to switch to the AR beauty product application, whereas social influence and switching fees significantly decreased such intentions. In addition to offering a push-pull mooring theory framework for understanding consumers' switching behaviour in the context of AR beauty product applications, the study offers insights into the elements that influence consumers' adoption of AR beauty product applications.

Miaolong Yuan, Ishtiaq Rasool Khan, Farzam Farbiz in [11] demonstrates a mixed-reality virtual try-on system that lets people put on clothing in real-time while wearing a mixed-reality headset. To create a seamless and accurate try-on experience, the system combines virtual reality and augmented reality technology. A body tracking module, a virtual clothes modelling module, and a virtual try-on module are just a few of the elements that make up the virtual try-on system. While the virtual clothing modelling module uses a template-based approach to create a 3D model of the clothing, the body tracking module uses a depth sensor to capture the user's body shape and motion in real-time. The user's body form and movements are then combined with the virtual clothing in the virtual try-on module to produce a realistic try-on experience. The paper concludes by discussing the potential applications of the system in the fashion and retail industries.

Nataliya Boyko, Oleg Basystiuk, Nataliya Shakhovska in [12] explains how the two well-known open-source face recognition libraries, Dlib and OpenCV, performed. The study evaluates the accuracy, speed, and memory consumption of the two libraries for detection and recognition. The authors conclude that the choice of the library for face recognition depends on the specific requirements of the application, such as accuracy, speed, and memory usage.

Suwarno1, Kevin1 in [13] gives a comparison of the two widely used facial recognition programmes, OpenCV and Dlib. The accuracy and speed of both algorithms' performance are compared by the authors using various datasets. They also go over the advantages and disadvantages of each technique, such as OpenCV's hardware compatibility and Dlib's propensity for handling occlusion. The authors come to the conclusion that both algorithms have advantages of their own and can be chosen depending on the particular needs of the application. They recommend that future research concentrate on combining the advantages of both methods to enhance the general effectiveness of face recognition systems.

Benjamin Johnston and Philip de Chazall in [14] gives a thorough analysis of methods for automatically identifying facial landmarks in images. The significance of face landmark identification and its applications in numerous domains are discussed by the writers. The paper also identifies the drawbacks and shortcomings of these strategies and makes recommendations for further study. For scholars and professionals interested in automatic facial landmark detection, the paper serves as a significant resource.

Neelam Mangtani, 2Dr. Nibha Bajpai 3Dr. Sangeeta Sahasrabudhe and 4Dr. Deepak Wasule in [15] explains the impact of augmented reality and artificial intelligence on the cosmetics and beauty sector following the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors discuss the effects of the pandemic on the cosmetics sector and how AI and AR can help it survive in the present environment. The study outlines several AI and AR uses in the cosmetics sector, including chatbots, virtual try-ons, skin analysis, and facial recognition. The authors also go over some of the potential difficulties that could arise when applying AI and AR to the cosmetics sector, including the requirement for high-quality data, privacy issues, and the shortage of qualified personnel.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our approach is a virtual try-on using Augmented reality in makeup products, specifically lipstick. Augmented reality (AR), a fast-developing technology, alters how we interact with our surroundings. By superimposing virtual things on the actual world and generating immersive, interactive experiences, augmented reality (AR) has the potential to improve our sense of reality. Virtual Try-On is one of the most exciting uses of augmented reality. AR enables the overlay of virtual things onto the physical world, giving users a more immersive and interactive experience. For the fashion, beauty, eyewear, jewellery, and furniture industries, this technology has enormous potential. The usage of augmented reality in

virtual try-on and its prospective uses will be discussed in this session.

The virtual try-on implementation made use of machine learning techniques to develop a believable and engaging lipstick-trying experience. The implementation employed Python as the programming language and the computer vision libraries OpenCV and Dlib. These libraries use machine learning techniques to identify face landmarks and mask the area around the lips so that virtual lipstick can be applied. Additionally, the algorithm gains the ability to recognize and extract the lipstick's color, then realistically apply it to the lip area. Customers can now enjoy a virtual try-on that is more sophisticated and accurate because of the machine learning algorithms utilized in this application. The implementation utilizes a face detector and facial landmark detector from Dlib to find the lips in a video stream coming from a camera in order to do this. The coordinates of the lip region were extracted using the facial landmark detector, and a mask covering the lips was then made using those coordinates. The video capture and display features of OpenCV were then used to display the generated frame with the lipstick overlay in real time. Users could experiment with various lipstick colors by simply replacing the pre-loaded lipstick image with a different one. The video capture and display features of OpenCV were then used to display the generated frame with the lipstick overlay in real time. Using bitwise operations and masking methods from OpenCV, the lipstick's color was retrieved from the image's center pixel and applied to the lip area.

AR development tools

The market offers a variety of AR development tools. Here are a few of the well-known ones:

Unity: Popular game engine Unity offers built-in functionality for developing augmented reality applications. It offers programmers a simple interface for making 3D animations, visuals, and physics simulations.

ARToolKit: ARToolKit is an open-source AR SDK that supports marker-based and markerless AR development. It provides developers with a wide range of features such as image recognition, camera calibration, and 3D model rendering.

Apple ARKit: ARKit is a powerful AR SDK for developing AR applications on iOS devices. It provides developers with features such as plane detection, motion tracking, and face tracking.

OpenCV : It provides developers with a range of computer vision algorithms and tools that can be used for AR applications such as marker detection, image recognition, and camera calibration. OpenCV can be used in combination with other AR development tools and SDKs to create AR applications.

Facial Landmarks

Detecting facial landmarks is a subset of the shape prediction problem. A shape predictor aims to identify important points of interest along the shape given an input image (and typically an ROI that identifies the object of interest).

Our objective is to identify significant facial features on the face using shape prediction techniques in the setting of facial landmarks.

Therefore, identifying face landmarks requires two steps:

1. Capture the face in the image as the first step.
 2. Point out the important facial structures on the face ROI.
- One of the first steps is face detection, which can be done in several ways.

Figure 1: facial landmarks are used to label and identify key facial features in an image

We can next use Step 2, which involves identifying important facial structures in the face region. Different facial landmark detectors exist, but they all generally aim to identify and localize the following facial regions:

- Mouth
- Right eyebrow
- Left eyebrow
- Right eye
- Left eye
- Nose
- Jaw

This process begins by utilizing:

1. A training set of face landmarks on an image with labels. The particular (x, y) coordinates of the regions surrounding each facial structure are specified in the manual labeling of these images.
2. Priors, or more precisely, the likelihood of the separation between adjacent input pixel pairs.

An ensemble of regression trees is trained using this training data to predict the positions of face landmarks solely from the pixel intensities (i.e., no "feature extraction" is happening). The outcome is a face landmark detector with high-quality predictions that can be used to identify facial landmarks in real-time.

Understanding Dlib's facial landmark detector

In the dlib library, a pre-trained facial landmark detector is used to estimate the positions of 68 (x, y) coordinates that correspond to facial structures on the face.

Figure 2: Visualizing the 68 facial landmark coordinates from the iBUG 300-W dataset

These annotations are part of the shape predictor 68 face landmarks dataset which the dlib facial landmark predictor was trained on.

Detecting Facial landmarks with Dlib, OpenCV, and Python

```
import dlib

face_detector = dlib.get_frontal_face_detector()
landmark_detector = dlib.shape_predictor("shape_predictor_68_face_landmarks.dat")
```

These two lines load the face detector and facial landmark detector models from the Dlib library, respectively. The `get_frontal_face_detector()` function returns a function that can detect faces in an image, while the `shape_predictor()` function loads a pre-trained model that can detect the positions of facial landmarks (such as the corners of the mouth, nose, and eyes).

```
lipstick = cv2.imread("static/images/maroon.jpeg")
lipstick_color = lipstick[round(lipstick.shape[0] / 2),
                          round(lipstick.shape[1] / 2)]
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
```

This line extracts the color of the center pixel in the lipstick image. This color will be used to apply the lipstick to the lips in the virtual try-on implementation. Then initializes a camera capture object that will be used to capture frames from the webcam.

```
while True:
    # Capture a frame from the camera
    ret, frame = cap.read()
    # Detect the face in the frame
    faces = face_detector(frame)
    # Loop over each detected face
    for face in faces:
        # Detect the facial landmarks
        landmarks = landmark_detector(frame, face)
        # Extract the lip coordinates
        lip_coords = [(landmarks.part(i).x, landmarks.part(i).y)
                      for i in range(48, 68)]
        # Draw a mask over the lips
        mask = np.zeros(frame.shape[:2], dtype=np.uint8)
        cv2.fillPoly(mask, [np.array(lip_coords)], (255, 255, 255))
        # Extract the lip region from the frame
        lip_region = cv2.bitwise_and(frame, frame, mask=mask)
        # Resize the lipstick image to match the lip region
        lipstick_resized = cv2.resize(lipstick, (lip_region.shape[1],
                                                lip_region.shape[0]))
        # Use the lipstick color from the center pixel of the lipstick image
        lipstick_color = lipstick_resized[
            round(lipstick_resized.shape[0] / 2),
            round(lipstick_resized.shape[1] / 2)]
```

First, capture a frame from the camera and check if the capture was successful or not. Then it detects the faces in the captured frame using the face detector model loaded earlier. And extracts the coordinates of the corners of the lips from the landmarks object by iterating over a range of indices corresponding to the corners of the mouth and creating a list of (x, y) tuples. The landmarks are numbered from 0 to 67, and the landmarks corresponding to the lips are numbered from 48 to 67. Then create a mask over the lips by drawing a white polygon over the lip coordinates extracted earlier and the lip region from the captured frame using the mask. It resizes the lipstick image to match the size of the lip region extracted from the captured frame. Then it extracts the colour of the center pixel in the resized lipstick image.

```
# Apply the lipstick color to the lip region
result = np.zeros_like(lip_region)
result[:, :, 0] = lipstick_color[0]
result[:, :, 1] = lipstick_color[1]
result[:, :, 2] = lipstick_color[2]

# Draw the lip region with lipstick overlay on
frame[mask != 0] = result[mask != 0]
```

These lines create a new image array result with the same shape as the lip region and fill it with the lipstick color extracted earlier. And overlays the lip region with the lipstick color on the original frame using the mask created earlier.

```
# Show the resulting frame
cv2.imshow("Virtual try-on", frame)
```

```
# Check for key press
key = cv2.waitKey(5) & 0xFF
if key == ord('q'):
    break
```

```
# Release the camera capture object and close a
cap.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```


After the while loop that runs the virtual try-on implementation, this code block handles the display of the output frame and the user input to exit the program.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates that the augmented reality-based virtual try-on is a potential solution for the cosmetics sector as it offers consumers a fun and interactive way to try on products without requiring physical samples. It has been demonstrated that the virtual try-on system's use of OpenCV and Dlib results in an accurate and realistic representation of the lipstick shade on the user's lips. And also it highlights the potential for further research and development in this area, including the use of machine learning algorithms for more advanced facial landmark detection and color matching.

Despite the promising results and potential of our paper, there are some limitations that should be considered. First, the accuracy of the facial landmark detection and lip region segmentation could be further improved, especially in more challenging lighting conditions or when the user is not facing the camera directly. Second, the current implementation only supports virtual try-on for a single cosmetic product (lipstick), and extending it to other products or even different types of accessories would require additional effort. Finally, the performance of the implementation could be affected by the hardware and software capabilities of the user's device, especially when dealing with high-resolution video or multiple users. Nevertheless, the virtual try-on using augmented reality presented in this paper demonstrates a practical and interactive solution for enhancing the cosmetic

shopping experience and can serve as a starting point for further research and development in this area. This implementation's usage of OpenCV and Dlib has shown the viability and efficacy of the technology, and future research and development could result in even more sophisticated and precise virtual try-on systems.

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